

HOW TO USE

SYMBOLIC OBJECTS

IN PROTEST, RESISTANCE
AND REBELLION

A GUIDE FOR SOCIAL MOVEMENTS

P E T E R
GARDNER

BENJAMIN
ABRAMS

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WHAT ARE SYMBOLIC OBJECTS?

Symbolic objects are physical items that carry strong symbolic meaning. They may serve as components in, targets of, or stimulus for protest action. They can be used to make declarations, represent groups, attract attention, inspire responses, stigmatise or legitimise actions, and imbue actors with authority, vulnerability, or other characteristics.

Protesters, rebels and revolutionaries often rely on objects imbued with symbolic content when taking action. Marchers parade flags and banners above their processions; striking workers hold placards declaring their grievances; some revolutionaries have used tulips, carnations, or roses as signifiers of their cause. These objects come in all shapes and sizes. They range from the 'Lennon walls' of communist Prague or boats at Extinction Rebellion protests to squares of red felt pinned to the clothing of the 2012 student fees protesters in Canada, and everything in between. More recently, statues have emerged as focal points for antiracist and decolonising movements, as well as in the reactionary backlash to 'protect' them. Across these examples and many more, symbolic objects act as powerful signifiers and strong motifs in protest, resistance and rebellion. In short, the objects we use in protest matter.

When activists use symbolic objects, knowingly or not they are engaging in potent meaning-making.

Symbolic objects have incredible power to spark change, and their use can make or break movements.

Thinking strategically about using symbolic objects has the potential to help activists tell moving stories, make powerful claims, and ultimately drive change.

SYMBOLIC OBJECTS as COMPONENTS OF PROTEST

Bringing a symbolic object to a demonstration, or utilising it as part of a rebellious or resistant action, allows it to form a component of protest. This can involve all sorts of physical things that are (for example) held or held up, waved, worn, stood upon, sheltered underneath, revealed or produced. They can work as practical tools, contextual props, or illustrative signals. They can make declarations about the nature of reality, mark out space, and represent unity of thought or solidarity with others. They can even do more than one of these things at the same time or switch between roles during a protest action.

EXAMPLES & CASE STUDIES

From movement placards to revolutionary armbands, from the coloured shirt in Thai riots to the machete in insurgencies across the African continent, and across the ubiquity of flags of all kinds in actions as disparate as LGBTQ+ pride parades, socialist revolutions, environmentalist protests, and workers' strikes, physical objects are found all over the place as components in collective action.

The 2003 Rose Revolution in Georgia reached its apex when the revolution's leader, Mikheil Saakashvili, led demonstrators to disrupt the national parliament in Tbilisi carrying **red roses** in their hands as a symbol of their cause. The image of the rose made the protests more spectacular and eye-catching, and served to readily identify disparate revolutionary actors with a single common cause.

In Oklahoma, 2015, activists challenged the installation of Ten Commandments statues in state-houses across the United States by donating and temporarily erecting an **8-foot bronze statue of Baphomet, a half-man, half-goat deity of the occult**, on behalf of 'the Satanic Temple of the USA'. The absurd, threatening visage posed by the statue undermined the taken-for-granted legitimacy of the Ten Commandments statues, and ultimately led to their removal by the Oklahoma Supreme Court, and a win for the activists, who then deployed the Baphomet statue in similar acts of resistance and protest in other US states.

Symbolic objects from the natural world can also serve as components in protest. **India's Chipko movement** in the 1970s involved activists **placing their bodies between old-growth Himalayan trees** and the industrial loggers who threatened to fell them. The visual image quickly gained iconic status, as photography of the trees encircled by their activist protectors spread around the world. The vision of trees being embraced, with both human and plant life threatened by logging machinery, came to speak of environmental compassion and solidarity with nature, leading to environmental activists becoming colloquially known as **'tree huggers'** for the remainder of the 20th century.

As symbols come to be aligned to specific movements, they are often appropriated for use outside of their original context. In US politics since 2016, Donald Trump's campaign and political rallies have involved the wearing of red 'MAGA hats' by his supporters. The red cap has since begun to diffuse, with anyone wearing a red cap of any kind potentially taking on the identity (mistakenly or not) of a Trump-supporter, white nationalist, or far-right sympathiser.

★ KEY POINT

The meanings attached to objects can be powerful allies for activists and protesters. Mobilising objects with established meanings can add powerful emotions and associations to a protest or act of resistance. Alternatively, activists can 'stick' new meanings to objects in ways that permit them to transgress the boundaries of their earlier use and emerge as important in other social and political contexts. Crucially, different meanings and ideas can stick to objects in ways that their original users may not have expected.

CONSIDER

What objects do you currently involve in acts of protest, resistance or rebellion? Are there new objects you could integrate into these forms of contention or old objects to which you can bring new symbolic associations? How can you capitalise upon objects' material and symbolic properties?

SYMBOLIC OBJECTS as TARGETS OF PROTEST

Objects are often some of the most visible targets of collective action, with activists aiming to alter, appropriate, juxtapose or even destroy them. As targets, symbolic objects become the site of compelling political displays.

EXAMPLES & CASE STUDIES

Objects as targets can be seen in the recent attempts by antiracist protesters to take down Confederate flags in many US states, the toppling of controversial statues in societies throughout the world, and the throwing of red paint over fur coats by animal rights activists.

After the Suffragettes engaged in window-smashing to demand votes for women, **the smashed window** itself emerged as a symbol of militant feminist action. Similar examples include the burning of racist passbooks in Apartheid South Africa, which led to the passbook — and its burned ashes — becoming hotly contentious symbols.

Causes need not always destroy or remove targeted objects, there are many cases where activists have added new objects to targeted places and spaces, often to great effect. Activists may also simply **add something** to their targeted object, be it graffiti on a memorial wall, or a traffic-cone hat on a once commanding statue.

KEY POINT

Targeting an object can further amplify its importance in a given struggle, or create a new point of vulnerability. When objects become targets, activists also have an opportunity to change or add meaning to them by physically acting upon them or modifying them. At times, objects that 'belong' to the powerful — literally, symbolically, or both — can be coopted into objects of resistance.

CONSIDER

Does your cause target particular objects, or are there objects you could potentially target? How could you take greater advantage of actions against them while avoiding drawing popular resentment?

SYMBOLIC OBJECTS as

A STIMULUS FOR PROTEST

Symbolic objects have the power to inspire contentious action. They can encourage new people to join a protest, mobilise lifelong activists, and generally bring people to the streets. This can trigger new rounds of protest or it can help spread a movement's cause by inspiring others to replicate actions and activism.

EXAMPLES & CASE STUDIES

In the United Kingdom, the 2019 European Parliament elections saw the rise of the practice of **'milkshaking' far-right figures**. A milkshake was thrown at far-right leader Tommy Robinson by an activist in May 2019. The milkshake became at once an innocuous drink and a method of figuratively covering objectionable politicians in disgust. This humiliating image of Robinson covered in the drink inspired others to 'milkshake' a variety of politically reactionary elites in other anglophone countries such as the US and Ireland.

When the South African state responded to the 1976 Soweto school protests with brutal force, the limp body of **Hector Pieterse** being carried away from the scene came to embody the inhumanity of apartheid regime. This poignant and emotive image was capitalised upon by activists to provoke not only a further round of **Black resistance** in South Africa itself, but a rise in international solidarity movements worldwide.

In France, the compulsory motorist's yellow vest was selected by activists as the uniform — and namesake — for the country's **'gilets jaunes'** protesters. This strategic decision allowed the vest to serve as a lingering stimulus for protest, always present in the glovebox of any French driver's vehicle, just waiting to be worn in refutation of government authority, an opportunity that would be regularly taken up for years to come.

KEY POINT

By thinking carefully about the availability, visibility and emotional impact of an object, activists can get a sense of its likelihood of stimulating contentious action. This is not always easy to figure out, but the big possible impact means it is always worth considering.

CONSIDER

What objects might help stimulate participation in your cause?
How might their visibility or impact be magnified?

HOW TO USE SYMBOLIC OBJECTS EFFECTIVELY

Movements have a variety of symbolic objects available for them to use in protest. Some of these may belong to them, others may be targets in the hands of their opponents. All of these belong to a 'strategic toolbox' from which activists can draw to protest for change, resist oppression, or rebel against injustice.

CONSIDER

Think about the objects you could add to your movement's strategic toolbox. Being deliberate about their use, creation or recruitment will maximise your potential impact.

Are there objects that are **already associated** with your activism or movement? How visible and well-known are they? Are they readily available?

Are there **practical purposes** some objects might serve, such as shields, equipment, props, or uniforms? Could these be given new symbolic associations?

Are there objects that encourage **powerful emotions**? What do they inspire, and how can they be used in protest?

Perhaps your movement faces restrictions from anti-protest laws. Could a symbolic object capture public attention and get across your message while bypassing these limitations?

Are there objects that create **important associations** with other causes, ideas or values? How might these be mobilised?

CONSIDER

Different objects can play different roles in your toolbox. Some can play more than one role.

Some objects will be useful **components** in protest, readily expressing an idea or creating a beneficial association.

Others will be useful **targets**, onto which activists can project new meanings, or through which they can expose an opponent's weak-spot.

Others will serve as a **stimulus** for further action, bringing new people to the cause or inspiring new allies in different places.

Some objects can even be a 'triple threat': a **target** of protest, a **component** in those protests, and a **stimulus** for further action. The Apartheid passbook is one such example.

Try to think a few steps ahead of those who will interpret your movement's symbolic objects.

How might these objects be **represented or misrepresented** by your opponents?

Are there any different or **unexpected interpretations** that might arise?

How much **influence** do you have over how people will understand the symbolic aspects of an object?

Is there anything you can do to or with the object that could **manage its interpretive scope**?

CALL TO ACTION

You and your movement probably already think carefully about the objects you use in protest actions. Our goal in producing this guide is to spark new ideas and help you think through some of the important elements involved in using objects in protest, resistance and rebellion, and ultimately to maximise the benefit of using symbolic objects in achieving social change.

If you organise an action or protest that draws on the information provided in this guide, we would love to hear from you. Please get in touch with us using the following contact details:

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SymbolicObjects.99

Secure message:
Scan the QR code to
message on Signal

We are still trying to further understand the roles that symbolic objects play in protest, resistance and rebellion. We're always looking for more examples to study, so we can answer further questions on how these things work. If you are organising an action or protest in the UK that uses a 'symbolic objects' approach, it would be fantastic if we could study the event as it happens. If you're interested in helping us out with this, please get in touch!

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